
An Analysis of Socioeconomic Factors Influencing Citizens Participation in Environmental Conservation Protocols

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the correlation between socioeconomic factors and citizens participation in environmental conservation and governance. To achieve its aim, three questions and a hypothesis were proposed. The study was conducted in seven (7) purposively selected communities in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. Survey method was used to collect primary data; a well-structured questionnaire was administered on 350 respondents extracted through the simple random sampling method to illicit useful information. Both descriptive and statistical techniques were utilized to analyze such collected data. The results of the descriptive analyses showed that citizens with higher socioeconomic status were more likely to participate in environmental conservation and governance, and that community-based initiatives and environmental awareness programmes would promote participation among citizens from different socioeconomic backgrounds. Also, results of the coefficients of the multiple regression of the influence of socioeconomic factors on participation revealed that all the t-values were greater than the tabulated value 1.645 at 5% level of significance; and the P-value 0.000 was less than the significant 0.005; agreeing with the decision of the ANOVA test, which accepted the alternative hypothesis. The findings underscore the need for targeted interventions that would address socioeconomic disparities and promote inclusive participation. Finally, the study's results have implications for policymakers seeking to promote environmental sustainability and community engagement for enhanced citizens participation in developing initiatives aimed to improve environmental conservation in human settlements.

KEYWORDS: Socioeconomic factors, Citizens' participation, Environmental conservation, Community-based initiatives, Conservation protocols.

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INTRODUCTION

The world, particularly the Niger Delta area is facing unprecedented environmental challenges, including but not limited to climate change, biodiversity loss, indiscriminate waste disposal and pollution, which poses significant threat to human well-beings and the environment; with noticeable low level of citizens participation in environmental management policies and programmes. In response to those environmental challenges, the ideals of environmental conservation have become a critical global priority, with governments, organizations, communities and individuals working together to promote the practice of conservation. A key aspect of effective environmental conservation is citizens' participation, which involves individuals and communities taking or playing active roles in environmental conservation practices.

According to Leighninger (2012), citizens participation in environmental conservation is essential because it would help in promoting environmental awareness and education, which are critical for changing behaviours and attitudes towards the environment. However, despite the importance of citizens participation in environmental conservation, there are significant challenges in promoting participation, particularly among certain socioeconomic groups in the study area. Whereas, researchers, such as Ongon et al, (2023), have argued that factors such as age, income, education, occupation and gender, can influence the individuals' abilities and willingness to participate in environmental conservation practices, can the assertion also be correct for citizens in the study area.

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It is against this backdrop that this study aims to establish the correlation between socioeconomic factors and citizen's participation in environmental conservation practices in the study area, and suggest measures that would engender more inclusive and effective environmental conservation efforts. To achieve the aim of the study, the following research questions were proposed:

- i. What are the socioeconomic factors influencing citizens participation?
- ii. How does socioeconomic factors affect citizens participation in environmental conservation?
- iii. What are the factors militating against citizen participation in environmental conservation practices?

THEORETICAL/CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This study drew its theoretical framework from the social exchange theory (SET); a framework for understanding human behaviour and relationships rests on the idea that people engage in exchange with others to minimise their costs and maximise their benefits (Mashael,2024). He stated that researchers across multiple disciplines have appreciated the social exchange theory for its capacity to explain human interactions in multiple situations, including the area of environmental conservation (Mashael,2024). Furthermore, he noted that in environmental conservation context, SET can be applied to explain how individuals and communities make decisions about their participation in environmental conservation practices in relation to perceived benefits. According to Faisal (2016), by smearing SET to environmental conservation, researchers and audience can better understand the motivations and barriers to participation in conservation practices and design more operative programmes to promote sustainable development.

Likewise, Paul (2023), noted that SET in environmental conservation sights interactions with the environment as a cost-benefit analysis: individuals engage in pro-environmental behaviours when they perceive the reward; social approval, intrinsic satisfactions and economic gains. Furthermore, the author stated that the concept of SET accentuates that human relationships are driven by the desire for reciprocal gain and the exchange of resources. According to Paul (2023), the key principles of the SET include;

- i Reciprocity: individuals and communities are more likely to participate in environmental conservation if they perceive benefits or rewards.
- ii Self-interest: individuals and communities are motivated to participate in environmental conservation if it serves their self-interest, and
- iii Cost-benefit analysis: individuals and communities weigh the costs and benefits of participating in environmental conservation practices.

THE CONCEPT OF CITIZENS' PARTICIPATION

According to Irvin (2004), citizens participation is the process by which individuals, families and communities assume responsibility for their own welfare and develop capacity to contribute to their community's development by being involved in the decision-making process. The author holds citizens participation as a means to educate citizens to increase their competence; and a vehicle for influencing decisions that affect the lives of citizens. Nabatchi (2012), noted that in achieving effective citizen participation, certain roles are required from various critical stakeholders; on the part of the citizens, the roles include: a fair respectful and open process which allows everyone affected to have equal opportunity to participate; to be involved early enough in the process to influence the outcome; listening to all perspectives, attempting to understand opposing opinions, trying to reach compromise on difficult issues, to be able to be effectively part of the solution and to define a role in implementation as its appropriate.

Nonetheless, earlier authors, notably Arnstein (1969), defined citizen participation in terms of the amount of actual control the citizens have over policy decisions. He believed that without actual redistribution of power, citizens participation is an empty initiative and likely to fail: hence, encouraging it at significantly high level would offer enormous benefits. Similarly, Leighninger (2012), noted that citizen participation offers many instrumental benefits to citizens, communities, and government in terms of collectively determining the appropriate developmental trajectory suitable for their environment. Dietz (2008), outlined some benefits of citizens participation to include: help build consensus for developmental initiatives, increasing the effectiveness of developmental investments as it build on local knowledge and understanding of problems leading to better tailored intentions; expand local capacities of people as they learn to manage and negotiate development activities; potentially increase coverage as local people assume responsibility for on-going sustainability discourse and maximise the potential use of interventions and lead to a more inclusive initiative as it improve the opportunity for women as well as other discriminated groups to be actively involved. According to Green (2007), noted that the lack of citizen participation is a major constraint to effective environmental control measures of government at all levels.

Similarly, Nabatchi (2012), argued that it was no longer acceptable for the people affected by any development not to be involved in the process leading to its implementation. Krishnaswamy (2012), noted that citizens participation encompasses as a variety of approaches. The author recommended a participatory approach in public decision-making, and illustrated same in a continuum which ranges from nominal participation (information exchange) to full participation. However, the author averred that determining

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the approach and level of citizens participation in environmental conservation is correlated to the purpose for stakeholders' engagement.

THE CONCEPT OF ENVIRONMENT CONSERVATION.

According to Edwin (2023), environmental conservation is the protection and management of natural resources, such as air, water, soil, plants and animal. The authors also noted that conservation seek to maintain the diversity and integrity of ecosystems and the services they avail humans and other living beings. Some of the benefits of environmental conservation according to the Edwin (2023) include:

- Enhancing the quality and availability of water, air and soil.
- Supporting the livelihood and cultures of indigenous and local communities.
- Preserving the genetic diversity and evolutionary potentials of species.
- Maintaining the aesthetics, recreational and spiritual values of nature.
- Reducing the risks and impacts of natural disasters, such as floods, drought, landslides and wildlife.
- Mitigating the effects of climate change by storing carbon and regulating temperature.

However, the pursuit of environmental conservation is not without challenges. Edwin (2023) highlighted such challenges to include; issues of balancing the competing demands and interests of different stakeholders, such as governments, businesses, NGO's and local communities; difficulties in addressing the root causes and drivers of environmental degradation, such as population growth, poverty, illiteracy amongst other socioeconomic factors; securing adequate funding for conservation initiatives; monitoring and evaluating the outcomes of conservation interventions and adapting to changing environmental conditions and emerging threats.

SOCIOECONOMIC FACTORS AND PARTICIPATION IN ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION

According to Hussain, Mohi Uddin Qadri et al (2025), the relationship between socioeconomic status (SES) and environmental behaviour is crucial for understanding the broader dynamics of environmental conservation. Consequently, guidelines for environmental conservation recommended education and public relationships to make people aware of their roles and responsibilities to the environment, so that they can change their behaviour to promote environmental quality (Ongon et al, 2023). According to Poboan (2012), everyone must play helpful roles to restore the environment, reduce pollution to its tolerable minimum and create awareness for everyone to give attention to environment related issues. The author stressed that citizens perception in conservation is strongly influenced by how individuals perceive the environmental consequences of their actions; therefore, suggested the need for enhanced awareness programmes, change of attitude and behaviour as well as improved socioeconomic status.

Ivkovic and Mandic (2024), asserted that limited access to environmental knowledge and education reduces the citizens capacity to engage in environmentally sustainable practices. In the view of Guo et al (2024), the degree to which individuals prioritize environmental conservation may vary significantly based on their access to education, employment and income. As such, addressing socioeconomic disparities is essential for understanding environmental behaviour, particularly in regions with noticeable inequalities. According to Hussain, Mohi Uddin Qadri et al (2025), higher SES is often associated with greater access to resources, enabling individuals to exhibit more sustainable behaviour, while lower SES may limit access to such opportunities; exacerbating environmental inequalities (Gifford & Nilsson, 2014).

According to Zreik (2023), financial and other socioeconomic constraints in less developed countries incumber prioritization of environmental conservation, reflecting the challenges of balancing economic needs with sustainability. Socioeconomic factors such as age, education, place of current residence, occupation, mental status, income and household size etc, are known to have impact and influence on the behaviour of the people towards the adoption of environmental conservation regimes (Hassan, 2006). Likewise, Faisal (2016), noted that socioeconomic factors such as income, education, occupation, etc, significantly influence the extent and nature of citizen participation in environmental conservation practices.

Nevertheless, the impact of these socioeconomic factors can be complex and multidimensional, with effects sometime contradicting each other between individuals and communities, and varying based on national context. Therefore, understanding the socioeconomic factors affecting people environmental opinion remains an essential element to conserving environmental or natural resources (Olawoye, 1996).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Study Area: The study area entails seven (7) communities; Diebu, Akama-ama, Peremabiri, Ikainbiri, Olugbobiri, Ekowe and Negiama, all are coastal communities along the Diebu creek oilfield in Southern Ijaw local government area of Bayelsa state. The communities were selected randomly. The geology is made up from top to bottom with Benin, Agbase and Akata formations (SPDC, 1998); and lie in the wet equatorial climate region of the Niger Delta. The area experiences both dry and wet seasons, with

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temperature ranging between 23 and 32°C with little monthly variations. The major economic activities of the area are agriculture, including: fishing, farming, forestry, lumbering, hunting, gathering of wild forest products and tapping of palm wine and brewing of local gin (Allison-Oguru, Zuofa & Berepubo, 1999). However, the area is rich in natural resources which include oil and gas, with oil wells in all communities and pipelines transversing the area.

Research Design: The research used mainly primary data, which involved the utilization of a structured questionnaire to illicit relevant data and direct physical observation. As earlier stated, the research involved seven (7) oil and gas bearing communities in Southern Ijaw local government area (SILGA) of Bayelsa State. Given the total population of the study area, the sample size of 350 was determined using the Taro Yamene formula for determination of sample size (Kpolovie, 2011). The multi-stage sampling technique was adopted for the study. A set of 350 multi-item questionnaires which had three sections: A-socioeconomic characteristics of respondents; B-citizens participation in environmental conservation and C- environmental awareness respectively, were administered to respondents who were both male and female, and household heads. The data obtained from the administration of questionnaires were analyzed descriptively (percentages, means and graphical illustrations), and the analysis of variance (ANOVA) and multiple regression analysis were adopted to test the only hypothesis of the study.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

As earlier stated, a total of 350 questionnaires were returned and subjected to proper data analysis. The results are presented in tables, both bar and pie charts amongst others; and in three sections: A-socioeconomic characteristics of respondents; B-citizens participation in environmental conservation and C- environmental awareness, as earlier stated.

Section A: Socioeconomic characteristics of respondents

Table 1: Age brackets of respondents

S/No	Age bracket	Frequency	Percentage
	1-40	-	
	11-20	-	
	21-30	15	4.2
	31-40	54	15.4
	41-50	97	27.7
	51-60	123	35.1
	60 and above	61	17.4
		350	100

Source: Researcher fieldwork, 2026

The Table showed that 15(4%) of respondents were within the age bracket of 21-30 years, 54 (15%) were within 31-40 years, 97 (28%) were within 41-50. The Table also showed that 123 (35%) of respondents were within the age bracket of 51-60 years, and 61(17%) of respondents were within 60 years and above.

Table 2 : Gender of respondents

S/No	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
	Male	326	93.1
	Female	16	4.5
	Undecided	8	2.3
		350	100

Source: Researcher fieldwork, 2026

Table 2 showed that 326 (93%) of respondents were male; 16 (5%) were female. Meanwhile, 8 (2%) of respondents declined to answer the questionnaire.

Table 3 : Education level of respondents? (Select one)

S/No	Level of education	Frequency	Percentage
	Primary level	41	11.7
	Secondary	134	38.2
	Tertiary level	119	34.0
	Post graduate	37	10.5
	Others (specify)	19	5.4
		350	100

Source: Researcher fieldwork, 2026

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It could be seen from the table that 41(12%) of respondents attained primary school level of education, 134 (38%) attained Secondary school level; 119 (34%) attained tertiary level. The table also showed that 37 (11%) of respondent were educated up to post graduate level and 19 (5%) attained other forms of education and training such as NCE, OND, and HND and related educational trainings.

Table 4 : Occupation of respondents

S/No	Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
	Farming	78	22.2
	Fishing	71	20.3
	Trading	33	9.4
	Civil Servant	84	24.0
	Artisan	50	14.3
	Company worker	27	7.7
	Others (specify)	7	2.0
		350	100

Source: Researcher Fieldwork, 2026

On occupation of respondents, table 4 showed that 78 (22%) were farmers, 71 (20%) were fishers, 33 (9%) were traders and 84 (24%) were civil servants. The table also showed that 50 (14%) were artisans, 27 (8%) were company workers and 7 (2%) of respondents were involved other forms of livelihood activities.

Table 5: Monthly Income of respondents.

S/No	Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
	less than 70,000	70	20.0
	70,000 - 79,000	105	30.0
	80,000 - 89,000	90	25.7
	90,000 - 99,000	51	14.6
	100,000 + above	34	9.7
		350	100

Source: Researcher Fieldwork, 2026

The table revealed that 70 (20%) of respondents earned less than 70,000; 105 (30%) earned between 70,000 - 79,000; 90 (26%) earned between 80,000 - 89,000. Also, the table showed that 50 (15%) of respondents earned between 90,000 - 99,000 and finally 34 (10%) of respondents earned 100,000 and above, as their monthly income from various livelihood sources.

Section B: Citizens' participation in environmental conservation practices

Table 6: Participation in environmental conservation activities in community

S/No	Option	Frequency	Percentage
	Yes	109	31.1
	No	214	61.2
	Undecided	27	7.7
		350	100

Source - Researcher's Fieldwork, 2026

The table showed that 109 (31%) of respondents stated that they participated in environmental conservation practices in their communities, while overwhelming 214 (61%) indicated non-participation. However, 27 (8%) of respondents declined providing any answer to the question.

Table 7: Type of environmental conservation activities participated (Tick as applicable)

S/No	Options	Frequency	Percentage
	Waste management	48	37.6
	Tree planting	21	19.3
	Water conservation	15	13.8
	Forest/wildlife conservation	20	18.3
	House management	12	11.0
	Others (Specify)		
		48	100

Source: Researchers fieldwork, 2026

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Table 7 showed that 41 (38%) of respondents stated that they participated in waste management practices in their communities; 21 (19%) indicated tree planting; 15 (14%) participated in water Conservation: practices, 20 (18%) indicated participation fast/wildlife conservation practices, and lastly, 12 (11%) of respondents indicated participation in noise control practices.

Table 8: Frequency of participation in environmental conservation activities (Tick One)

S/No	Option	Frequency	Percentage
	Daily	29	8.2
	Weekly	43	12.3
	Monthly	59	16.8
	Rarely	19	5.5
	Never	200	57.1
		350	100

Source: Researcher fieldwork, 2025

The table revealed that 29 (18%) of respondents indicated that they participate in environment conservation practices on daily basis, 43 (12%) indicated weakly participation, 59 (17%) stated that they participate on monthly basis, 19 (16%) stated that they rarely participate in environment consideration activities. However, and indeed worrisomely, 200 respondents accounting for 57% stated that they never participated in environmental conservation practices in their communities.

Section C: Environmental Awareness

Table 9: Most pressing environmental problem in the community

S/No	Environmental problem	Frequency	Percentage
	Loss of biodiversity	78	22.2
	Indiscriminate waste dumping	102	29.1
	Indiscriminate logging	47	13.4
	Loss of agricultural land	31	8.8
	Flooding/Hyacinth invasion	50	14.2
	Soil/shore erosion	25	7.1
	Water pollution	17	4.8
	Others (Specify)		
		350	100

Source: Researcher fieldwork, 2026

As showed on Table 10, 78 (22%) of respondents stated that the most pressing environmental problem in their commences was loss of biodiversity, 102 (29%) indicated indiscriminate dumping and wastes, 47 (13%) indicated indiscriminate logging activities. The table also showed that 31 (9%) of respondents indicated loss of agriculture land as most pressing environmental problem; 50 (14%) stated flooding/hyacinth invasion, whereas 25 (7%) stated soil/shore erosion; 17(5%) of respondents stated that water pollution was the most pressing environmental problem in their communities.

Table 10: Rate level of environmental awareness! (Tick one)

S/No	Option	Frequency	Percentage
	High	66	18.8
	Medium	157	44.8
	Low	116	33.1
	Undecided	11	3.1
		350	100

Source: Researcher Fieldwork, 2026

Table 10, showed that 66 (19%) of respondents indicated that their level of environmental awareness was High; 157(45%) indicated their environment awareness level to be Medium; and 116 (33%) rated their environmental awareness level to be Low. However, 11(3%) of respondents declined providing any answer.

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Table 11: Received any environmental education

S/No	Option	Frequency	Percentage
	Yes	100	31.4
	No	212	60.5
	Undecided	28	8.0
		350	100

Source: Researcher Fieldwork, 2026

The table revealed that 100 (31%) of respondents stated that they have received environmental education/training; 212 (6%) stated that they have not received any form of environmental education/training. However, 28 (8%) of respondents declined providing any answer to the question.

Table 12: Constraints to participation in environmental conservation practices

S/No	Possible Factor	Frequency	Percentage
	Lack of public awareness	47	13.4
	Low income (poverty)	72	20.5
	Low education (illiteracy)	99	28.2
	Lack of regulatory agencies	27	7.8
	Nature of occupation	54	15.4
	Age	51	14.6
		350	100

Source: Researcher Fieldwork, 2026

On constraints to participation in environmental conservation practices, 47 (13%) of respondents stated lack of public awareness; 72 (21%) stated low-income level; 99 (28%) of respondents stated low level of education. The table also showed that 27 (8%) of respondents stated lack of regulatory agencies, 54 (15%) stated nature of occupation/work and 51 (15%) of respondents indicated age limitation as a major constraint to participation in environmental conservation practices.

Table 13: Willingness to participate in environmental conservation practices

S/No	Option	Frequency	Percentage
	Yes	257	73.4
	No	69	16.8
	Undecided	34	9.7
		350	100

Source - Researcher Fieldwork, 2026

On willingness to participate in environmental conservation practices in their communities, 257 (73%) of respondents indicated willingness to participate and 59 (16%) indicated unwillingness to participate. However, 34 (10%) declared providing any answer.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

The research hypotheses were tested using appropriate statistical tool;

- i. H₀₁: Socioeconomic characteristics of the citizens significantly affect participation

Table 14: Multiple Regression of the influence of socioeconomic characteristics on participation

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.962 ^a	.925	.924	.172

Source: Field Survey, 2026

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Household size, Highest Educational Qualification, Age Bracket, Occupation, Monthly Income. The multiple regression analysis was applied to assess the adequacy of the fitted regression model. It gives the overall prediction power of the model. The result indicates that 0.962(96.2%) of the variation in the model has been explained by the independent variable in the model.

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Table 15: F-Statistics (ANOVA) of the Multiple Regression of the influence of socioeconomic characteristics on participation

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	121.140	5	24.228	822.935	.000 ^b
	Residual	9.833	334	.029		
	Total	130.974	339			

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Dependent Variable: Participation

Predictors: (Constant), Household size, Highest Educational Qualification, Age Bracket, Occupation, Monthly Income.

Test of goodness of fit for regression model

$$Y = B_0 + B_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + B_3X_3 + B_4X_4 + B_5X_5 + e$$

$$Y = 0.684 + 0.136X_1 + 0.168X_2 + 0.512X_3 + 0.085X_4 + 0.228X_5$$

The ANOVA approach is applied to examine the overall influence of the explanatory variable X on the independent variable Y

Y=Dependent variable

X=Independent variable

B₀=Intercept

B₁=Regression coefficient

e=Error

The ANOVA revealed that F-ratio value 822.935 is greater than the tabulated value 3.84 at 5% level of significant and also, the p-value 0.000 is less than the 0.05 significant levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative accepted.

Table 16: Coefficients of the Multiple Regression of the influence of socioeconomic characteristics on participation

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.684	.033		20.481	.000
	Age Bracket	.136	.031	.201	4.359	.000
	Highest Educational Qualification	.168	.025	.357	6.818	.000
	Occupation	.512	.018	1.284	27.972	.000
	Monthly Income	.085	.023	.199	3.728	.000
	Household size	.228	.042	.334	5.416	.000

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Dependent Variable: CP

The coefficient table 16 revealed that all the t- values for B₁, B₂, B₃, B₄, B₅, were greater than the tabulated value 1.645 at 5% level of significant and also, the p-value 0.000 is less than 0.05 level of significant. This implies that all the coefficients are significant and this agrees with decision of the ANOVA test.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed that socioeconomic factors such as age, educational attainment, occupation, income status, etc, significantly influenced citizens' levels of participation in environmental conservation programmes. The results also revealed that citizens with higher socioeconomic status, particularly those with higher incomes and education levels were likely to participate more in environmental conservation practices; this is shown in tables 14, 15 and 16 respectively. This position is in line with the view of Guo et al (2024), who posited that the degree to which individuals prioritize environmental conservation may base on their access to education, employment and income amongst other socioeconomic factors.

On constraints to participating in environmental conservation programmes, greater percentage of respondents identified low educational level, low-income status, nature of occupation, age etc, as major factors militating against their effective participation, as shown in table 12. However, and quite interestingly greater percentage of respondents, precisely 73% expressed willingness to participate in environmental conservation practices in their settlements. Also, the study's findings showed that environmental

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awareness and education play a crucial role in promoting citizens' participation in environmental conservation practices, underscoring the importance of environmental education and awareness programs in empowering citizens to make informed decisions about environmental conservation responses. Therefore, results of the study underscore the need for community-based infrastructure and participatory approaches to environmental conservation, which builds trust and foster a sense of ownership among citizens.

RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

Consequent upon the research findings, the following recommendations would suffice:

1. Government should invest in environmental education and awareness programmes that would promise environmental literacy and encourage citizens participation in environmental conservation practices.
2. Government should provide resource and support to promote environmental conservation practices, including funding for environmental projects, training and capacity - building programmes and technical assistances.
3. Environmentalist should develop programs that are inclusive of citizens from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds, and that take into account the specific needs and concerns different individuals and communities.
4. Environmentalists should build partnerships with community groups, local organisations and other Stakeholders to promote environmental consideration practices and foster a sense of ownership amongst citizens.
5. Community leaders shall empower local committees to take ownership of environmental conservation practise, and provide them with the necessary resources and support to do the needful.

The implications of this study are far-reaching, as policymakers, environmentalists, and community leaders can draw on its findings to inform the design and implementation of environmental conservation programmes. By understanding in socioeconomic factors that influence citizens participation in environmental conservation practices, policy makers can develop targeted interventions that can address the specific needs and concerns of different socioeconomics groups. We believe that this can help to promote more inclusive and effective environmental conservation efforts, which are critical for achieving sustainable development and environmental sustainability in settlements constituting the study area.

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